

Deliverable Phase 2 – Climate risk assessment

CMV4Clima - Context specific climate risk assessment and adaptation strategies for the Valchiavenna Alpine territory

This document summarizes the activities carried out by the Mountain Community during the second phase of the project. These activities include: communication actions undertaken to share project results with stakeholders; dissemination actions targeting educational institutions and local environmental associations; communications with public authorities such as Regione Lombardia, the Province of Sondrio, and BIM (Mountain Catchment Basin Authority); articles published in regional media mentioning the project; project dissemination activities carried out during other events; and project communication on social media.

For the majority of the activity a supporting links is provided.

Communication actions taken to share results with your stakeholders

3/04/2025 – Conference for local stakeholders/citizens regarding CLIMAAX project and biodiversity

https://cmvalchiavenna.it/cmchiavenna/po/mostra_news.php?id=264&area=H

Dissemination actions focused on educational establishments, environmental territorial associations (WWF, Legambiente), forestry consortiums, cooperatives

01/04/2025 – Meeting with Valchiavenna high school classes – Istituto di Istruzione Superiore Leonardo da Vinci

Communications with public authority: Regione Lombardia, Provincia di Sondrio, Bim (mountain catchment basin)

13/06/2025 – Video conference with Lombardy Region - Civil protection Organizational Unit

17/07/2025 - Conference of Mayors of Valchiavenna

Articles in regional media mentioning the project

01/09/2025 - Touring club monthly magazine

<https://cmvalchiavenna.it/cmchiavenna/images/Inserito%20touring.pdf>

Project dissemination actions during other events

25-26/06/2025 – Interreg Europe EURADAPT project - Kick off meeting

15/09/2025 – Interreg ALCOTRA - thematic workshop

23/09/2025 – ENCORE Network – partner conference in Goteborg

26/09/2025 - Erasmus meeting with Polish teachers and public authority

4/11/2025 – “Rapporto Montagne Italia 2025” presentation

Project communication on social media

03/04/2025 [Facebook](#) post about Conference for local stakeholders/citizens regarding CLIMAAX project and biodiversity

04/04/25 [Instagram](#) post– about the conference for local stakeholders regarding CLIMAAX project and biodiversity

13/06/25 [Instagram](#) post – CMV4Clima project presentation during Horizon conference in Barcellona

14/06/25 [Instagram](#) post - CMV4Clima project presentation during Horizon conference in Barcellona

06/11/25 [Instagram](#) post- - Rapporto Montagne presentation

27/11/25 [Linkedin](#) post – CLIMAAX success story

6/11/2025 [Linkedin](#) – Rapporto Montagne presentation

[Project communication on the institutional website](#)